

UCD Chemistry Celebrates Global Women's Breakfast 2026

Report by: T. N. Hooper*

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Venue: UCD O'Brien Science
Centre, Dublin

Event Type: Cultural Event

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<http://zenodo.org/communities/ice/>

Organising Committee: T. N. Hooper,^a K. Stanley,^a F. M. Fung.^a

^a School of Chemistry, University College Dublin, Ireland.

Organisation: University College Dublin School of Chemistry – Equality, Diversity and Inclusion Committee

Event Sponsors

The event was sponsored by the Royal Society of Chemistry Republic of Ireland Local Section and the Royal Society of Chemistry Equality and Diversity Fund. Thanks also to IUPAC and the UCD School of Chemistry.

Summary

The event hosted by the University College Dublin School of Chemistry Equality, Diversity and Inclusion (EDI) Committee was to celebrate the IUPAC Global Women's Breakfast (GWB) 2026. This is a recurring international event with similar celebrations taking place across the world and is timed to coincide with the UN International Day of Women and Girls in Science. The theme of this year's GWB was "Many Voices, One Science". This GWB event at UCD was the only one in Ireland and the aim was to celebrate the role of women in the UCD School of Chemistry and in science more widely, to promote gender equality in the workplace, build professional networks and support mentor/mentee relationships. The event was designed to be informal and allowed social interaction and networking throughout all members of the School of Chemistry. Five screens around the event space played the IUPAC video showcasing the global participation of GWB and the student-run UCD Chemistry Society created their own video showing UCD students saying the phrase "Many Voices, One Science" in their native languages, highlighting the diversity of backgrounds amongst the students. Screens also displayed

information about the School of Chemistry EDI committee and related EDI information. Short speeches highlighted the importance of the event and the EDI work in the School of Chemistry. A "mentoring and inspiration" wall was made where attendees were encouraged to write names of people (particularly women) who had helped or inspired them in their science careers. Overall, the event was a success with a very good number of participants from different levels and excellent feedback to the post-event survey.

Attendees

The informal event had approximately 60-70 participants including staff (academic, research, technical and administrative), students (postgraduate and year 3 and 4 undergraduate) from the UCD School of Chemistry and a small number of RSC members from nearby universities (DCU). The event was to celebrate the Global Women's Breakfast 2026, but all genders were encouraged to attend to participate in this global event. The diversity of the UCD School of Chemistry staff and students was well represented. The event was free to attend with no registration needed to promote participation, fully accessible (step

free access) and advertised as widely as possible via several methods to encourage engagement from all groups.

Target audience: Staff (academic, research, technical and administrative), students (postgraduate and year 3 and 4 undergraduate) from the UCD School of Chemistry and local RSC members

Programme

The event featured brief remarks from several members of the UCD School of Chemistry. Prof. James Sullivan welcomed participants to the GWB event and highlighted the commitment of the UCD School of Chemistry and UCD more widely to equality, diversity and inclusion. Dr Kristy Stanley as chair of the UCD School of Chemistry EDI Committee described the work of the committee. Postgraduate student Celine Erkey spoke about the importance of female role models. Postgraduate student Fabian Hollinger talked about the Gaelic Mentors initiative being run in 2026 by the Fung lab to support undergraduate students. Dr Tom Hooper shared news of the recent Athena Swan Silver Award received by the UCD School of Chemistry and highlighted the ongoing commitment to promote gender equality.

Feedback

Feedback on the GWB event was collected via an anonymous online survey. Of 31 responses collected, the feedback was overwhelmingly positive. 93% of respondents either agreed or strongly agreed that they enjoyed the event and it enhanced their sense of community. 87% either agreed or strongly agreed that the UCD School of Chemistry has strong female role models and positive responses were also given to the implementation of EDI initiatives and policies in the School.

“Good job. Encouraging and positive atmosphere for all genders.”

February 10, 2026
GWB 2026
Many Voices, One Science

The School of Chemistry EDI Committee will host our first
IUPAC Global Women's Breakfast

We invite School of Chemistry academic staff, technical officers, administrators, research funded staff, graduate research students, taught MSc students and Chemistry BSc Stage 3 and 4 students of all genders to come together to celebrate the diversity of voices in our field, honour the achievements of role models in science, and inspire the next generation

Date: Tuesday, 10th February 2026
Time: 11:30 am
Venue: 3rd Floor Science East
Refreshments: Food is provided!

Arrive hungry and ready to chat, celebrate the contribution of women and connect with people around the world.

This Event is Supported by:
ROYAL SOCIETY OF CHEMISTRY
Equality and Diversity Fund
RSC LOCAL SECTION
REPUBLIC OF IRELAND

Figure 1. Poster advertising the UCD School of Chemistry GWB Event.

Acknowledgements

Thanks to UCD ChemSoc for creating the UCD “Many Voices, One Science” [video](#) played at the event. Thanks to the UCD School of Chemistry administrative team for helping with organisation and set up.